

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ENERGY SECTOR BASED ON WIRELESS SYSTEMS

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Abstract. Providing uninterrupted power supply to railway transport facilities has significant costs for the construction of distribution networks. This paper proposes the use of microgrid technology based on wireless technologies, which will provide a reliable power supply. Implementation of these systems will reduce consumption of energy resources, reduce the time of detection and elimination of solutions in case of failure in power grids, reduce losses in power distribution.

Keywords: microgrids, 5G technology, energy, smart city technology.

Аннотация. Обеспечение бесперебойным электроснабжением объектов железнодорожного транспорта имеет значительные затраты на строительство распределительных сетей. В данной работе предлагается использование технологии микросетей на основе беспроводных технологий, которые обеспечат надежное энергоснабжение. Внедрение этих систем позволит снизить потребление энергоресурсов, сократить время обнаружения и устранения решений при сбойных ситуациях в энергосетях, сократить потери при распределении электроэнергии.

Ключевые слова: микросети, технология 5G, энергетика, технология «умный город».

Annotatsiya. Temir yo'l transporti ob'ektlarini uzluksiz elektr energiyasi bilan ta'minlash taqsimlash tarmoqlarini qurish uchun katta xarajatlarni talab qiladi. Ushbu hujjat ishonchli energiya ta'minotini ta'minlaydigan simsiz texnologiyalarga asoslangan mikrogrid texnologiyasidan foydalanishni taklif qiladi. Ushbu tizimlarning joriy etilishi energiya sarfini kamaytirish, energiya tarmoqlaridagi nosozliklarni aniqlash va bartaraf etish vaqtini qisqartirish, elektr energiyasini taqsimlashda yo'qotishlarni kamaytirish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: mikrotarmoqlar, 5G texnologiyasi, energiya, aqli shahar texnologiyasi.

Introduction

At the present time, due to the growth of electricity consumption, a great deal of attention is being paid to the energy industry. The demand for consumption is related not only to population growth, but also to new models of technology, such as electric cars, portable devices and Internet services.

With the increase in renewable energy sources comes the need to design distributed networks such as microgrids. The use of 5G wireless networks will make it possible to create a network of sensors for controlling the distribution networks of electricity, water and gas resources. The introduction of these systems will reduce the consumption of energy resources, reduce the time of detection and elimination of emergency situations in power grids, and reduce losses in the

distribution of electricity. Recently, the energy system is being unbundled into small grids, which will not depend on the overall energy system. They are replaced by alternative power sources (solar panels, wind generators, micro hydro, etc.), which have their own capacities. Individual energy areas will be controlled by individual sources, which are synchronized with the overall energy system.

Microgrids are one of the options for alternative energy sources

Due to the growth of loads on power systems, it is becoming difficult to distribute and control electricity consumption. Therefore, there is a need for alternative power sources and their metering with the help of microgrids. In this regard, there is a growing need for the use of "green" generation for various devices performing highly specialized purposes.

All this destabilizes the power grid, and there are high costs when using additional capacity in the centralization of electricity. Therefore, microgrids are created on the basis of energetically isolated townships. Microgrids make it possible to synchronize different individual energy sources and stabilize the power grid based on 5G technology. This allows high-speed data transmission and solves the problem of microgrid development. The task of developing microgrids based on combined power sources and wireless data transmission is relevant[1].

Smart grid and its possibilities

Smart grid will maximize the use of energy resources and respond quickly to various emergencies.

The operation of the energy microgrid is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Operation of a stationary energy microgrid

The power system consists of substations, relays, current leads, and various complex equipment that are already difficult to manage. It takes a lot of skilled personnel to operate and maintain. Recently, "smart" robots or drones have been used. They detect problems, monitor the operation of equipment with cameras, glasses. With the growth of energy systems, renewable or, as it is called "green energy", there is a need for a new generation microgrid based on 5G. with the help of 5G you can build a model to predict the amount of energy production and consumption.

The introduction of 5G in the energy sector will change electricity rates, reduce the cost of data transmission, create virtual electricity storage, and manage a huge number of "green" energy installations.

Building a 5G network for the energy industry

The goal of the work is to build a 5G network for the needs of the energy industry.

Consider building 5G, the fifth generation of wireless technology for the needs of electrical facilities. There are various ways of implementation. The most advantageous is the network based on a three-tier technology region - district - city.

The 5G wireless system is based on EMBB (Enchanted Mobile Broad Band) mobile communications. This connection provides access to multimedia applications: ultra-HD, 3D video, online games, advanced and cloud services, streaming and music. For large transmission systems: Minot Machine Type Communication. These applications are used for transmitting small amounts of information that is little affected by time delays. Figure 2 gives a breakdown of 5G into network layers.

Fig.2. Dividing 5G into network layers

This technology can be used not only in the energy sector, but also in transport, medicine and trade. Another way to build a 5G network is to use reliable transmission systems with minimal time delay using URLLC (Ultra Reliabland Logo Latency Communications) application. This technology can be used to automate power distribution in smart grids, smart homes and cities, as well as in the transportation industry to connect electric vehicles to a common network based on V2X (Vehicle to Every Thing). A variant of the 5G wireless network deployment is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Deployment of the 5G network

The 5G technology shown in Figure 3 operates in the 694 MHz to 790 MHz band, which provides connectivity beyond the line of sight because of the large coverage area. Frequencies from 1 GHz to 6 GHz provide connectivity for large cities. For areas with large coverage and the

largest number of subscribers, communications are provided in the 24 GHz to 86 GHz frequency range[2].

Various 5G applications allow you to connect water meters, electricity meters, household devices ("smart" home), create a "smart" office, video surveillance system ("smart" city), control individual energy devices. With the help of 5G it is possible to remotely control equipment, provide support for vehicles, automatically control driving (unmanned vehicles).

Stages of construction of 5G technology in the energy industry

There are several stages in the construction of 5G technology. The first stage is the interaction with the existing 4G networks of the LTE standard. It is carried out by EN-DC (e-utran new radio dual connectivity) and NGN-DC (ng-ran-e-utran new radio dual connectivity). This will ensure joint operation with subscriber devices (UE, User equipment) with 4G and 5G networks.

The second stage is the improvement of LTE-EN gNB base stations and the EPS (Evolved Packet Core) network. This stage is tantamount to building a 5G core network.

In the third stage, it is necessary to upgrade the eNB base station network to ng-eNB, that is, to switch it to a 5G network, which corresponds to the construction of base stations gNB.

The last step is to dismantle the EPS network equipment. This operation can be performed on condition of communication between the backbone network and subscribers.

In the near future, many energy challenges are likely to be solved. Robots and 5G open up opportunities to increase speeds, the quality of information transmitted, and increase the reliability of power equipment.

The Global ICT Energy Efficiency Summit, held in Amsterdam, the Netherlands, discussed trends in energy strategy and solutions. Huawei presented a white paper titled 5G Targeted Energy Networks and 5G Targeted Data Centers to provide optimal energy solutions.

5G technology has now been launched - video at 1,376 Mbps.

Conclusion

1. The introduction of 5G technology involves managing, scaling networks with a huge number of connections, which will be provided with intelligent network functions.
2. 5G makes it possible to create a high-speed highway, manage power consumption and distribution.
3. Next-generation mobile networks can create microgrids that can reduce power consumption.
4. 5G networks provide reduced time to update and troubleshoot electrical equipment.
5. 5G networks can drive unmanned vehicles.
6. The implementation of 5G will lead to the digitalization of the energy industry.

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